

1 **The role of the estimand framework in the analysis of patient-**
2 **reported outcomes in single-arm trials: a case study in oncology**

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2 **ABSTRACT**

3 **Background** Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) play an increasing role in the evaluation of
4 oncology treatments. At the same time, single-arm trials are commonly included in
5 regulatory approval submissions. Because of the high risk of biases, results from single-arm
6 trials require careful interpretation. This benefits from a clearly defined *estimand*, or target
7 of estimation. In this case study, we demonstrated how the ICH E9 (R1) estimand
8 framework can be implemented in SATs with PRO endpoints.

9 **Methods** For the global quality of life outcome in a real single-arm lung cancer trial, a
10 range of possible estimands was defined. We focused on the choice of the variable of
11 interest and strategies to deal with intercurrent events (death, treatment discontinuation
12 and disease progression). Statistical methods were described for each estimand and the
13 corresponding results on the trial data were shown.

14 **Results** Each intercurrent event handling strategy resulted in its own estimated mean
15 global quality of life over time, with a specific interpretation, suitable for a corresponding
16 clinical research aim. In the setting of this case study, a ‘while alive’ strategy for death and a
17 ‘treatment policy’ strategy for non-terminal intercurrent events were deemed aligned with
18 a descriptive research aim to inform clinicians and patients about expected quality of life
19 after the start of treatment.

20 **Conclusions** The results show that decisions made in the estimand framework are not
21 trivial. Trial results and their interpretation strongly depend on the chosen estimand. The
22 estimand framework provides a structure to match a research question with a clear target

1 of estimation, supporting specific clinical decisions. Adherence to this framework can help
2 improve the quality of data collection, analysis and reporting of PROs in SATs, impacting
3 decision making in clinical practice.

4

5 **KEYWORDS**

6 Patient-reported outcomes, single-arm trial, estimand, quality of life, oncology, repeated
7 measurements

8 **A.1 Background**

9 Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) play an increasingly important role in the evaluation of
10 treatments(1). In the assessment of anti-cancer therapies, PROs are particularly relevant
11 since the therapies are often aimed at prolonged survival and an improvement in quality of
12 life (QoL) and/or symptom reduction. Regulatory authorities such as the US Food and Drug
13 Administration (FDA) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) have published
14 guidelines on how to incorporate PROs in studies submitted for cancer therapy
15 approval(2–9). Guidelines for the inclusion of PROs in trial protocols and scientific
16 reporting guidelines for PROs in clinical trials have also been developed(10,11).

17 Results from single-arm trials (SATs) are becoming more prominent in the regulatory
18 approval for oncology medicines, especially in rare cancer types for which there is not yet
19 an effective standard of care, late-stage cancer, and for targeted therapies suitable only to a
20 subgroup of patients with a specific mutation. One-third of the trials involved in FDA
21 approval of oncological therapies between 2014 and 2019 were single-arm studies(12).

1 Although in some situations a carefully designed SAT is the most ethical or feasible option,
2 results from SATs require careful interpretation because of the high risk of biases and the
3 absence of concurrent control(13,14). This is a particular concern for PRO endpoints where
4 dropout may be associated with the outcome measured.

5 Careful interpretation of an estimate calls for a clearly defined target of estimation, also
6 called an “estimand” by the International Council for Harmonization (ICH). The ICH have
7 set out their “estimand framework” in an addendum (R1) to their guideline E9 on
8 Statistical Considerations for Clinical Trials(15). The framework aligns the design and
9 analysis of a trial with its aims. Fiero et al. have shown how the estimand framework may
10 be used to translate a PRO-related research question into a fully defined estimand in a
11 hypothetical randomized trial(16).

12 In a recent literature review on SATs in oncology that reported PROs(17), only two of the
13 included studies specified a research hypothesis for the PROs. Intercurrent events in
14 relation to the analysis of PROs were not discussed in any of the studies. The collection of
15 PROs often stopped after treatment discontinuation, limiting the possibilities of a
16 ‘treatment policy’(15) or intention-to-treat analysis. Linear mixed models or other
17 (implicit) imputation methods were used in many studies without acknowledging how the
18 implicit imputation affected the interpretation of the results(17). The intercurrent event of
19 death is of particular concern here since PROs after death do not exist and implicit
20 imputation after death is counterintuitive.

21 This case study was undertaken within the work package on SATs of the SISAQOL-IMI
22 consortium, which aims to develop recommendations on design, analysis, presentation, and

1 interpretation for PRO data in cancer clinical trials(18). Our objective was to demonstrate
2 how the estimand framework can be implemented in SATs with PRO endpoints.
3 Specifically, we focused on global health-related QoL measured in a SAT in non-small cell
4 lung cancer(19). In this paper, we present a range of possible choices of estimand,
5 corresponding statistical methods, and their implications retrospectively using
6 anonymized data from a real single-arm cancer trial.

7 **A.2 Methods**

8 In this section, we first briefly describe the design of the clinical trial used for illustration in
9 this case study, in particular regarding PRO data collection. After touching on how missing
10 PRO data were handled, we discuss the various estimands that were illustrated in this case
11 study and the corresponding statistical methods for estimation. All statistical analyses were
12 performed using R(20) and analysis code is available as an online supplement.

13 **A.2.1 Trial design**

14 The single-arm, multicenter phase 2 trial evaluated the efficacy, safety, and tolerability of a
15 new anticancer treatment in patients with locally advanced or metastatic anaplastic
16 lymphoma kinase (ALK)-positive non-small cell lung cancer. The co-primary outcomes of
17 the trial were objective tumor response (as per RECIST V1.1) and adverse events (using the
18 National Cancer Institute Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events, V.4.0).

19 In addition, several PROs were assessed as secondary endpoints, of which we focused on
20 the overall QoL as measured by EORTC QLQ-C30 global QoL scale. We will refer to this PRO
21 as “global QoL.” The global QoL scale of the EORTC QLQ-C30 was scored according to the

1 EORTC scoring manual(21) such that scores ranged from 0 (representing the worst) to 100
2 (best possible score). In the original study, a clinically relevant difference of 10 points in
3 mean QoL compared to the mean at the start of protocol treatment was defined(19). The
4 trial was conducted before the estimand framework was developed, and no strategy to deal
5 with intercurrent events or missing PRO data was explicitly mentioned in the paper.

6 **A.2.2 Collection of PRO data in the trial**

7 While on trial medication, participants were asked to complete the EORTC QLQ-C30
8 questionnaire on the first day of protocol treatment and every three weeks while on
9 protocol treatment. The tri-weekly intervals were aligned with the treatment cycles of
10 chemotherapy, which was the standard of care for this disease setting. We therefore refer
11 to the timing of PRO measurements with their cycle number and baseline is defined here as
12 the first day of cycle 1. After cycle 10 (30 weeks), the study protocol allowed for completion
13 of the questionnaire on the first day of alternate cycles (i.e., every six weeks).

14 With respect to PRO data collection, three types of intercurrent events occurred in the
15 study: progression of disease (PD), treatment discontinuation (TD, mostly due to disease
16 progression), and death. Although disease progression was often followed by the
17 discontinuation of treatment in the trial, it was left to the discretion of the physician and
18 patient to decide when to stop the treatment. Upon discontinuation of trial medication,
19 patients were asked to complete one final questionnaire, after which PRO data collection
20 was ended, while only follow-up for overall survival continued. The sponsor anonymized
21 the measurements before a subset was shared with us for this case study.

1 **A.2.3 Methods for missing PRO data**

2 **A.2.3.1 Description of missing data**

3 For each cycle, we summarized the number of patients in each of the following six states: 1.
4 alive, on treatment and QoL available; 2. alive, on treatment and QoL not available; 3. alive,
5 off treatment and QoL available (this was extremely rare); 4. alive, off treatment and QoL
6 not available; 5. lost to follow-up for overall survival (and QoL); 6. deceased. In the rare
7 case when there was more than one PRO measurement reported by the same patient in one
8 cycle, we averaged the patient's PRO measurements in that cycle. As intercurrent events
9 play an important role in the definition of an estimand, the availability of PROs before and
10 after intercurrent events was also analyzed descriptively.

11 **A.2.3.2 Imputation of missing data**

12 In line with our illustrative aim, we created one (reasonably realistic) complete dataset in
13 which the implementation of the estimand framework could be studied. To this end, we
14 applied a single imputation method (Appendix A.1). We observed a general drop in PRO
15 scores in the last five cycles before death, whereas no such drop was observed before
16 censoring. The progression of disease and the decision to discontinue treatment may be
17 related to patients' QoL trajectories as well. We therefore assumed that the time-distance
18 to death and other intercurrent events was relevant to the missing PROs at each cycle.

19 We imputed missing PRO data using single imputation (see Appendix A.1 for details) for
20 each participant until cycle 40 or death, whichever occurred first, under the assumption
21 that the PROs at each cycle were missing at random conditional on the cycle number,
22 available QoL measurements at other cycles, death, PD and TD, and the time until these
23 events. Missing values were imputed before and after PD and/or TD, but not after death.

1 We assumed non-informative censoring in our analyses, as most censoring was
2 administrative at study end.

3 **A.2.4 Applying the estimand framework in our case study**

4 We introduced various estimands (i.e., targets of estimation) for describing global QoL over
5 time from the start of protocol treatment. As defined in ICH E9-R1, an estimand has five
6 attributes: the treatment, the population, the variable of interest, the population-level
7 summary, and a strategy for handling intercurrent events(15). In this case study, the
8 assigned treatment was the same trial medication for all participants, and we used the in-
9 and exclusion criteria of the original trial to define our target population of ALK positive
10 non-small cell lung cancer patients. Appendix A.2 provides a general discussion on defining
11 the variable, the population summary and the handling of intercurrent events for PROs in a
12 SAT. Below, we outline the estimands that were illustrated in this case study specifically, as
13 well as corresponding statistical methods for estimation (for a schematic overview see also
14 Table 1)

15 **A.2.4.1 Defining the variable and the population summary**

16 To illustrate the different variables of interest, we computed summaries of the numerical
17 value of the PRO, the change from baseline, and a responder/non-responder classification
18 at each cycle using the raw, unimputed data. We opted for the absolute numerical value of
19 the PRO for subsequent analyses(22–25). Because of the limited availability of the PRO
20 data in later cycles, we restricted our analyses to cycles 1-40 (months 0-27). Furthermore,
21 we opted for the mean QoL value at each cycle as the population summary. Since the
22 distribution of observed QoL was reasonably symmetric in exploratory analyses, the mean
23 was deemed to be an appropriate summary. For a range of intercurrent event strategies,

1 we applied a corresponding analysis (outlined below) to show how results and
2 interpretations differ.

3 **A.2.4.2 Strategies to deal with death**

4 In our illustrations of strategies to handle death in the analyses, we used all (imputed) data
5 after TD and PD, regardless of whether TD and PD had occurred, following a treatment
6 policy strategy. For transparency, we provided survival estimates with our global QoL
7 estimates, as well as estimates of the probability of remaining progression-free and of
8 remaining on protocol treatment.

9 *While alive strategy*

10 First, for each cycle, we estimated the mean QoL in the patients who were still alive in that
11 cycle. Note that over time the group in which the means are calculated becomes smaller
12 due to mortality and censoring, and may have a different distribution of characteristics
13 than the group who is alive at the first cycle. Therefore, we provided (Kaplan-Meier)
14 estimates of survival with the estimated means while alive. Essentially, we are interested in
15 a bivariate outcome here: survival and QoL conditional on survival.

16 The while alive estimates were obtained in two ways: (1) using generalized estimating
17 equations (GEE) with an independence correlation structure, which have been shown to
18 allow direct modelling of means over time conditional on survival status(26,27), and (2)
19 modelling the individual QoL values over time with a linear mixed model (LMM) followed
20 by averaging individually predicted QoL values only over those alive at each cycle(27). A
21 GEE analysis with an independence correlation structure, with time as a categorical
22 variable and without any approaches to handle missing data will yield the same means

1 over time as a purely descriptive approach. So, this GEE approach is in line with a
2 descriptive aim. In addition, the GEE models the means over time only, whereas the LMM
3 provides individual predictions that we averaged over the alive subject afterwards (since
4 using marginal means from the model directly would correspond to a hypothetical strategy,
5 see below).

6 *Composite strategy*

7 As an example of a composite strategy for death, all global QoL values after death were set
8 to 0, a value chosen somewhat arbitrarily for the sake of illustration here (cf. EQ-5D, a
9 health utility score where a value of 0 corresponds to death(28)). The means of this
10 composite outcome were estimated using GEE as above. Whether it makes sense to put
11 global QoL and death on the same scale, and to assign a value of 0 to death on this scale, is
12 debatable.

13 Different choices of the QoL variable of interest allow for other ways to define a composite
14 endpoint of QoL and death. For example, if a responder analysis is performed, death might
15 be included in the definition of nonresponse. In an analysis of time-till-deterioration,
16 deterioration may be defined as a drop in QoL or death. However, such analyses have their
17 limitations as discussed in Appendix A.2(22–25).

18 *Hypothetical strategy*

19 Finally, we estimated the mean QoL over time in a hypothetical situation where all patients
20 would remain alive until at least cycle 40. Two LMMs including the cycle number as a
21 categorical variable and 1) a random intercept only, or 2) a random intercept and slope,

1 and were fitted to the available data. Subsequently, marginal means for cycles 1 through 40
2 were obtained from the fitted models. These models assume that the QoL values of patients
3 who are no longer alive at a particular cycle are missing at random conditional on observed
4 QoL values and the cycle number. Under this assumption, LMMs (implicitly) extrapolate
5 QoL trajectories for each patient after their death to model a hypothetical scenario
6 assuming no deaths in the trial.

7 **A.2.4.3 Strategies to deal with treatment discontinuation**

8 Various strategies to handle TD in PRO data analysis were applied along with strategies to
9 handle death described above. Progression of disease was ignored here using a treatment
10 policy strategy for PD. We did not define a numerical composite outcome for TD, as
11 associating a single global QoL score with TD did not seem reasonable.

12 *While on treatment*

13 First, we implemented a while on treatment strategy, which implies a while alive strategy
14 since treatment does not continue after death. The mean QoL at each cycle (while on
15 treatment) was estimated by removing all observations after treatment discontinuation
16 from the data and fitting a GEE with independence correlation structure to the remaining
17 data.

18 *Hypothetical strategies*

19 Additionally, two hypothetical strategies were illustrated. For both strategies, an LMM was
20 fitted to all data before TD. For the first strategy, the model's predictions were averaged
21 over all patients at cycles 1-40. This resulted in estimated mean QoL in the hypothetical

1 situation assuming no treatment discontinuation or death in the study. For the second
2 strategy, we averaged the same model's predictions over the subset of patients who were
3 still alive at each respective cycle. This was intended to estimate the mean QoL while alive,
4 in the hypothetical situation where treatment discontinuation did not occur before death
5 within the study.

6 *Treatment policy strategy*

7 Finally, we applied a treatment policy strategy to TD, while alive. Here, we used the data
8 with (imputed) measurements after TD and applied GEE to estimate the mean QoL while
9 alive, regardless of TD. This is the same analysis as for the while alive method described
10 previously. As almost no data were available after TD, these estimates were mostly based
11 on imputed data at later cycles.

12 **A.2.4.4 Strategies to deal with disease progression**

13 Finally, we set the strategy for TD to a treatment policy strategy and shifted our focus to
14 the intercurrent event of disease progression (PD). We defined intercurrent event
15 strategies for PD analogously to those for TD.

Table 1 Combinations of intercurrent event strategies that were illustrated in this case study and their corresponding analysis methods

FIGURE	INTERCURRENT EVENT STRATEGIES				ANALYSIS	
	While no IE	Composite	Hypothetical	Treatment policy	QoL data included in the analysis*	Estimation of mean
FIGURE 3						
1A,B	Death			PD, TD	All outcomes until each patient's respective death in the first 40 cycles**, including outcomes after TD or PD.	1a. GEE with independent LMM per patient, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable. 1b. An LMM with independent LMM per patient, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable. In this LMM, the mean and variance-covariance matrix were estimated, where the mean was a vector of parameters for each categorical variable. The variance-covariance matrix was assumed to be the same for all categorical variables. The LMM was estimated over those patients who were not censored.
2A		Death		PD, TD	All outcomes until each patient's respective death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after TD or PD. After death, the outcome was set to 0 until cycle 40.	Estimated means for each categorical variable. Correlation structure for categorical variables. (Applying an LMM to each categorical variable.)
3A,B			Death	PD, TD	All outcomes until each patient's respective death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after TD or PD.	3a. Marginal means for each categorical variable, where the intercept, where the categorical variable was included as a categorical variable. 3b. same as 3a, but with the categorical variable included as a categorical variable.
FIGURE 4						
1	Death, TD			PD	All outcomes before each patient's respective TD or death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after PD.	GEE with independent LMM per patient, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable. Individual LMM per patient, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable. Each cycle also pooled over patients.
2A			Death, TD	PD	All outcomes before each patient's respective TD or death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after PD.	Marginal means for each categorical variable, where the intercept, where the categorical variable was included as a categorical variable.
2B	Death		TD	PD	All outcomes before each patient's respective TD or death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after PD.	Estimating an LMM for each categorical variable, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable.
3	Death			PD, TD	Same as estimates 1a,b in Figure 3.	
FIGURE 5						
1	Death, PD			TD	All outcomes before each patient's respective PD or death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after TD.	GEE with independent LMM per patient, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable. Individual LMM per patient, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable. Each cycle also pooled over patients.
2A			Death, PD	TD	All outcomes before each patient's respective PD or death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after TD.	Marginal means for each categorical variable, where the intercept, where the categorical variable was included as a categorical variable.
2B	Death		PD	TD	All outcomes before each patient's respective PD or death in the first 40 cycles, including outcomes after TD.	Estimating an LMM for each categorical variable, where the cycle number was included as a categorical variable.
3	Death			TD, PD	Same as estimates 1a,b in Figure 3.	

Table legend: *Assuming complete QoL data for each patient from study registration until death; to obtain such complete data (sets) likely requires imputation to be performed before the analyses listed here. **Some patients in the study were censored for overall survival.

censoring was mostly administrative at the end of the study, we assumed uninformative censoring in our analyses. If an informative censoring mechanism is plausible, weighted GEE approaches or joint models may be used to account for such censoring(26,27). PD: disease progression, TD: treatment discontinuation, GEE: generalized estimating equations, LMM: linear mixed model.

1 **A.3 Results**

2 **A.3.1 Inclusion and follow-up**

3 A total of 876 patients from the lung cancer SAT with at least one QoL or clinical
4 measurement were included in our analysis. This excludes patients from participating
5 centers not allowing the use of data for this purpose.

6 The median [IQR] follow-up time in those censored for overall survival was 41.8 [28.1-
7 47.3] months. Most censoring (72%) was near the data collection cut-off date. We therefore
8 assume that most censoring (for overall survival) was administrative censoring and
9 uninformative censoring was likely to hold. In a multivariable Cox regression, censoring
10 was not associated with sex, age, baseline ECOG performance status or the number of
11 previous therapies.

12 **A.3.2 Description of clinical characteristics**

13 Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants in our data were
14 summarized (Appendix A.3 Table S1). Death was observed in 576 (66%) patients. The
15 Kaplan-Meier estimate of median survival time was 21.7 months [95% CI 19.8-24.2], with
16 the probability of survival of 67% [95% CI 64%-71%] and 47% [95% CI 43%-50%] after
17 one and two years of the start of protocol treatment (A.3 Figure S2).

18 **A.3.3 Description of global quality of life**

19 At baseline, 834 (95%) of the patients filled in the QoL questionnaire. The mean (SD) global
20 QoL was 53.7 (25.2) at cycle 1. A positive association between QoL at baseline and overall

1 survival was observed (A.3 Figure S3, $p < 0.001$ for log-rank test where participants were
2 stratified based on four equal-length intervals of baseline QoL).

3 A.3.4 Description and imputation of missing PRO data

4 A.3.4.1 Availability of PRO data

5
6 *Figure 1. Availability of PROs over time, in relation to treatment and survival status. Note that*
7 *by design of the study, almost no PROs were reported after discontinuation of protocol*
8 *treatment. As a result, there are no to very few patients in state 2 at each cycle.*

9 The number of available PROs reduced to 538 (61%) by cycle 10 and 221 (25%) by cycle
10 20. In cycle 40, when the estimated survival probability was 43%, only 61 patients (7%)
11 were still alive and completed the QoL questionnaire (Figure 1). For this reason, we
12 restricted our further analyses to cycles 1-40.

1 The median time between the last available PRO and death observed during follow-up was
2 2.7 months (A.3 Figure S4). PRO data was available until less than 1 month before death for
3 140 patients (24% of observed deaths), and less than 3 months before death for 315
4 patients (55%). PRO measurements were mostly available until shortly before censoring of
5 the survival time: the median [IQR] time between the last available PRO and censoring was
6 1.59 [0.62-16.24] months.

7 PROs were collected until PD for most patients in whom PD was recorded (n=648). After
8 PD, 345 patients continued the trial medication for at least one month and 241 continued
9 for 3 months or more. Most (89%) patients reported a PRO measurement at the
10 discontinuation of protocol treatment. Eight patients had two PRO measurements post-
11 discontinuation, and one patient had three PRO-measurements after they discontinued
12 treatment.

13 **A.3.4.2 Imputation**

14 After imputation, the mean PRO in those alive at each cycle was slightly lower than in the
15 available data (A.1, Figure S1). Intercurrent events such as PD and (being close to) death
16 may lead to missing PROs and be associated with lower QoL. As our imputation model
17 takes such events into account, we would indeed expect global QoL in the imputed dataset
18 to be somewhat lower on average than in the available data, particularly at later cycles
19 when more participants have experienced PD and/or are in the final weeks of their life.

1 A.3.5 Illustration of the estimand framework

2 Below we show results corresponding to the estimands defined in Section A.2.4. Our focus
 3 is on the illustration of different variables of interest and on strategies to deal with
 4 intercurrent events, in particular death, TD and PD.

5 A.3.5.1 Defining the variable of interest: illustration

6 Our variable of interest was the absolute numerical value of the PRO. For illustration, we
 7 provide summaries of three possible variables of interest in our raw data: the absolute
 8 numerical value, the magnitude of change from baseline and a binary responder/non-
 9 responder classification at each cycle (Figure 2).

survival	1	0.88	0.8	0.72	0.64	0.58	0.51	0.47	0.43
PROs avail.	834	694	538	390	221	238	107	140	61

1 *Figure 2. Mean and 95% CI of three possible variables of interest, within available*
2 *(unimputed) data at each cycle. Top graph: absolute global QoL. Middle graph: difference in*
3 *global QoL from the start of protocol treatment. Bottom graph: responder classification,*
4 *where response for a patient is defined as an increase of at least 10 points in global QoL from*
5 *the start of protocol treatment.*

6 *3.5.1.1 The absolute (numerical or ordinal) values of the PRO*

7 The mean reported global QoL at the beginning was 54 (n=834), increased to 67 (n=654) in
8 cycle 4 and then appeared relatively constant until cycle 40. Note that the population with
9 available measurements shrinks over time from death and drop-out, mainly due to TD and
10 PD.

11 *3.5.1.2 Magnitude of change from baseline*

12 A downward trend in the mean change from baseline was visible after cycle 6 within the
13 available data. These results illustrate that when the mean QoL in those alive remains
14 constant, and there is a selection process over time where patients with high starting
15 values live longer, the mean change from baseline in those alive will decrease over time.
16 Regarding floor and ceiling effects, 33 patients (4.0% of available baseline measurements)
17 were at the lowest possible QoL level at baseline, whereas 43 patients (5.2%) had the
18 maximum possible global QoL score at baseline. The patients with the minimum possible
19 QoL at baseline cannot have a negative change by definition. At the same time, patients at
20 the top of the global QoL scale at the start can never have a positive change. This is
21 important to consider when interpreting the mean change from baseline.

1 3.5.1.3 Responder/non-responder classification

2 As an example, we defined response at each cycle as having an increase in at least 10 points
3 in QoL compared to baseline. A responder definition based on the magnitude of change
4 from baseline may also suffer from ceiling effects: in our example, participants with
5 baseline QoL values of 91 or higher could never be classified as a responder. The
6 proportion of responders at each cycle within those patients who reported PROs showed
7 an initial increase in the first four cycles and then a gradual downward trend.

8 A.3.5.2 Strategies for dealing with intercurrent events

9 For the intercurrent event strategies defined in Section A.2.4, we estimated the
10 corresponding mean global QoL at each cycle within the imputed dataset. The various
11 intercurrent event strategies resulted in diverging estimates, each with their own
12 interpretation.

13 3.5.2.1 Death

14 The estimated mean QoL while alive increased after treatment initiation and showed a
15 slight decreasing trend at later cycles (Figure 3). The GEE and the LMM with post-hoc
16 averaging yielded very similar results in this case. The composite estimates decrease
17 rapidly after cycle 4. This is due to death dominating the composite outcome with an
18 increasing proportion of patients with a QoL of 0 in the dataset.

19 Both hypothetical strategies resulted in estimated mean QoL values below the while alive
20 estimates. During the hypothetically extended part of the participants' lives, their average
21 QoL at each cycle was estimated to be lower than the average QoL of participants who were

1 alive in the same cycle. The model with the random intercept and slope resulted in lower
2 mean QoL estimates than the model with a random intercept only. The (linear) random
3 slope model fitted the data better (difference in AIC: 1510, p-value for likelihood ratio test:
4 <0.0001). Models with random effects for flexible spline functions of the cycle number
5 were unstable. Hence we could not test for nonlinear effects. Both models aim for the same
6 hypothetical estimand for death and both models extrapolate QoL after death. Yet *how* the
7 models extrapolate is determined by the model specification. No major differences in CI
8 width occurred between the various analysis methods used.

9 Regarding statistical efficiency, it is difficult to compare estimation methods that
10 correspond to diverging estimands, as these methods are not targeting the same quantity.
11 However, we observed no major differences in standard error magnitude between the
12 analysis methods illustrated in this subsection (A.3 Figure S5)

13

survival	1	0.88	0.8	0.72	0.64	0.58	0.51	0.47	0.43
progression-free	1	0.8	0.59	0.47	0.36	0.29	0.23	0.18	0.16
on treatment	1	0.78	0.63	0.53	0.42	0.36	0.29	0.24	0.2
PROs avail.	834	694	538	390	221	238	107	140	61

1

2 *Figure 3. Estimated mean global quality of life in each cycle for different estimands and*
 3 *corresponding models. The estimands differ in the chosen strategy to deal with the event of*
 4 *death in the analysis of the PROs. The two statistical methods applied to estimate mean QoL*
 5 *while alive (1a and 1b) overlap in the figure, as their resulting estimates were very similar.*

6 3.5.2.2 Treatment discontinuation

7 The estimated mean QoL while on treatment at each cycle was slightly higher than the
 8 while alive estimates ignoring treatment discontinuation (Figure 4). This reflects that QoL
 9 likely decreases to some extent after TD, as drivers of TD may also lead to decreasing QoL.
 10 The estimated means in a hypothetical situation without treatment discontinuation, while
 11 alive were higher than the means while alive (treatment policy). The estimated mean
 12 global QoL under a hypothetical strategy for both TD and death is lower than the while

1 alive estimate for each cycle. Confidence interval widths were similar, although the
 2 estimates for the treatment policy (while alive) strategy were somewhat more precise than
 3 the others (A.3 Figure S6). This could be due to the treatment policy estimates using all
 4 (imputed) data up to death, whereas the other estimates are based on data from before TD
 5 only.

survival	1	0.88	0.8	0.72	0.64	0.58	0.51	0.47	0.43
progression-free	1	0.8	0.59	0.47	0.36	0.29	0.23	0.18	0.16
on treatment	1	0.78	0.63	0.53	0.42	0.36	0.29	0.24	0.2
PROs avail.	834	694	538	390	221	238	107	140	61

6
 7 *Figure 4. Estimated mean global quality of life in each cycle for different estimands and*
 8 *corresponding models. The estimands differ in the chosen strategy to deal with the event of*
 9 *treatment discontinuation (TD) and death in the analysis of the PROs.*

1 3.5.2.3 Disease progression

2 Comparing the resulting estimates for disease progression (Figure 5) to those for
 3 treatment discontinuation (Figure 4), we note that QoL in the hypothetical world where PD
 4 does not occur in the trial is estimated to be higher than in the hypothetical world where
 5 TD does not occur. PD usually occurs earlier than TD in our dataset. Any drop in QoL after
 6 PD but before TD that is observed in the data is not taken into account by the linear mixed
 7 model in the first hypothetical scenario, since it is only fitted on observed values before PD.

survival	1	0.88	0.8	0.72	0.64	0.58	0.51	0.47	0.43
progression-free	1	0.8	0.59	0.47	0.36	0.29	0.23	0.18	0.16
on treatment	1	0.78	0.63	0.53	0.42	0.36	0.29	0.24	0.2
PROs avail.	834	694	538	390	221	238	107	140	61

8
 9 *Figure 5. Estimated mean global quality of life in each cycle for different estimands and*
 10 *corresponding models. The estimands differ in the chosen strategy to deal with the event of*
 11 *disease progression (PD) and death in the analysis of the PROs*

1 **A.4 Discussion**

2 In this case study, we have outlined the meaning and impact of the estimand framework in
3 the analysis of longitudinal PROs in a SAT. While the causal interpretation of SAT results
4 remains challenging due to a high risk of biases, the estimand framework facilitates a clear
5 definition of the aims and interpretation of a SAT analysis. Hence, the use of this framework
6 mitigates some of the methodological issues previously observed for PROs in SATs, such as
7 the lack of an explicit strategy to address intercurrent events(17).

8 The results of our illustration show that decisions made in the estimand framework are not
9 trivial. In particular, each intercurrent event handling strategy resulted in its own
10 estimated QoL means over time, with a specific interpretation, suitable for different clinical
11 research aims.

12 **A.4.1 The absolute numerical value of the PRO as the variable of interest**

13 The absolute numerical value of the PRO, change scores and responder classification as
14 possible endpoints of interest were illustrated on our dataset. The interpretation of change
15 scores or responder/non-responder classifications may be obscured by floor and ceiling
16 effects, a selection process due to death on baseline values, regression to the mean and the
17 non-definitive nature of changes in the PRO (see Appendix A.2 for more discussion).

18 Generally, the absolute numerical value of the PRO suffers from fewer drawbacks than
19 other options and is the most direct representation of the data(22–25), especially for a
20 descriptive study aim. A corresponding population summary might be the mean PRO at (a)
21 prespecified time point(s).

1 A.4.2 The while alive strategy and the use of LMMs and GEE

2 When dealing with death in the analysis of PROs, a while alive strategy most closely
3 represents the actual or observed situation. Any (implicit) imputation of PROs after death
4 implies that these values are missing and observable in principle. However, PROs after
5 death are neither observable nor defined. The assumption of a hypothetical world in which
6 patients do not die during the study was far removed from reality in our case study. This
7 hypothetical scenario may therefore not be clinically relevant, particularly in groups of
8 patients where the mortality rate is high. Especially in a SAT context, where the aim is often
9 descriptive, it makes sense to stay close to the experienced reality and use a while alive
10 strategy combined with an estimate of the survival probability. In a randomized trial
11 context, a drawback of the while alive strategy may be that differences in case-mix arise
12 between the trial arms over time because of differential survival. However, this would also
13 be the case in future implementations of the treatment in similar populations.

14 Crucially, marginal effects from a standard linear mixed model of PROs over time rely on
15 implicitly imputed PRO values after death. It is important for researchers to be aware that
16 the use of such a model implies a hypothetical estimand regarding death. For other
17 intercurrent events, fitting an LMM that does not account for intercurrent events may
18 correspond to different estimands depending on data availability. For example, if there are
19 no data after TD, fitting an LMM corresponds to a hypothetical strategy for TD and death,
20 whereas the same model may estimate a treatment policy estimand for TD if all data after
21 TD are available until death. Population means while alive can be obtained by averaging
22 individual predictions from a fitted LMM over those still alive. If direct estimates of

1 population level means are of interest in a while alive strategy, we recommend the use of
2 GEE with an independence correlation structure(26,27). The appropriate analysis will
3 depend on the trial objective and stakeholders.

4 **A.4.3 The treatment policy strategy for non-terminal intercurrent events**

5 For non-terminal intercurrent events such as treatment discontinuation, a treatment policy
6 strategy seems a reasonable choice, as it aligns with the intention-to-treat principle. Often,
7 it is relevant to know what to expect of a treatment, even after it is discontinued. Of course,
8 this depends on the trial aim, for example, a while on treatment strategy may be
9 appropriate for a tolerability objective. A treatment policy strategy for TD and PD requires
10 data collection after these events, which is often limited as in our case study. After
11 discontinuation of the trial treatment, patients may transfer to a different treatment center
12 and/or enter another trial. This complicates the observation of PROs after TD, especially in
13 single-arm trials and rare diseases. In this paper, we showed analyses where a ‘treatment
14 policy’-strategy was always applied to TD or PD (or both). Of course, other combinations
15 are possible, and the combination of strategies should be defined carefully.

16 **A.4.4 The composite strategy**

17 A composite outcome of a PRO (or any other outcome) and an intercurrent event may be
18 dominated by the intercurrent event(29,30). Examples of composite outcomes include the
19 EQ-5D measure(28,31) and Quality-Adjusted Life Years(32) or variants such as Quality-
20 adjusted Time Without Symptoms or Toxicity(33). For transparency, results from a
21 composite strategy should be accompanied by a measure of the incidence of the event.

1 Furthermore, the interpretation of a composite outcome is difficult when the intercurrent
2 event cannot be meaningfully put on the same scale as the PRO. For instance, to assign a
3 single value to QoL after someone's treatment has been discontinued, makes little sense. In
4 the composite strategies of this case study, the assumption of QoL at 0 after death (as is
5 also done in the EQ-5D measure(28)) is highly debatable and makes no sense from a
6 clinical point of view as patients do not experience QoL after death. While composite
7 endpoints may be common in some contexts such as Health Technology Assessment, we
8 suggest caution in assigning a single PRO value to death or other intercurrent events.

9 **A.4.5 Choosing the most appropriate estimand in a study**

10 The advantages and limitations of each estimand discussed above can be considered when
11 applying the estimand framework to PROs in a clinical study. The research setting
12 determines the most relevant estimand, depending on, for example, the stakeholders
13 involved, the type of PRO, and the PRO objective (e.g., to assess the efficacy or the
14 tolerability of a new treatment). If PRO data are intended for review of payer or regulatory
15 submission, discussions with these stakeholders to identify appropriate estimands and
16 analyses are highly encouraged.

17 Some studies explore more than one estimand to address multiple stakeholders. In that
18 case, we recommend clearly specifying the targeted estimand with each presented result,
19 for instance, in tables and figure legends. Estimates of different estimands have different
20 interpretations: they are not estimates of the same quantity. It is therefore important to
21 clarify the intended interpretation of each result when reporting on a study.

1 **A.4.6 Intercurrent events and the imputation of missing PROs**

2 Finally, we note that the choice of intercurrent event strategy and dealing with missing PRO
3 data are two separate but related topics. Intercurrent events may hinder the measurement
4 of PROs, causing missingness, and intercurrent events may be predictive for the missing
5 values, e.g., QoL may decrease at a time of disease progression. Conditioning on
6 information about intercurrent events in imputation may make a MAR assumption more
7 plausible.

8 In our analyses, we assumed non-informative censoring, as most censoring was
9 administrative at the end of the study. If an informative censoring mechanism is more
10 plausible, weighted GEE approaches or joint models may be used to account for such
11 censoring(26,27).

12 The single imputation method that we applied to address missing data was meant to
13 generate a single example dataset for illustration of the estimand framework. Multiple
14 imputation would better account for uncertainty in the missing values. An alternative way
15 to account for missing PRO data would be to reweight observations by the inverse
16 probability of missingness in the analysis. In addition, our MAR assumption may not hold.
17 Finally, there were virtually no data after treatment discontinuation, so the relation
18 between TD and PROs after TD could not be estimated from the data. Patients' health status
19 might deteriorate after treatment stops, but they may also switch to a new treatment that
20 improves their QoL. We plan to explore imputation methods for longitudinal PROs in the
21 presence of intercurrent events in detail in a future study.

1 **A.5 Conclusions**

2 This case study has illustrated possible estimand definitions when dealing with PROs in a
3 single-arm cancer trial and discussed considerations underpinning this choice. We have
4 also provided an overview of corresponding statistical methods for the estimation of each
5 estimand. Our findings show that trial analysis results and their interpretation strongly
6 depend on the chosen estimand. The estimand framework provides a structure to match
7 the research question in a trial with a well-defined target of estimation, supporting specific
8 clinical decisions. Adherence to this framework can help improve the quality of data
9 collection, analysis and reporting of PROs in SATs and thereby increase end-users' insight
10 and confidence in their results, impacting decision making in clinical practice.

11 **A.6 List of abbreviations**

- 12 ALK: anaplastic lymphoma kinase
- 13 EMA: European Medicines Agency
- 14 FDA: U.S. Food and Drug Administration
- 15 GEE: Generalized Estimating Equations
- 16 LMM: linear mixed model
- 17 MAR: missing at random
- 18 PRO: patient-reported outcome
- 19 QoL: quality of life
- 20 SAT: single-arm trial

1 TD: treatment discontinuation

2 PD: progression of the disease

3 **A.7 Declarations**

4 **A.7.1 Ethics approval and consent to participate**

5 No data were collected for the purpose of this study. Anonymized data from a previously
6 published trial were shared with us for the illustration of analysis methods, respecting the
7 informed consent previously provided by the trial participants.

8 **A.7.2 Consent for publication**

9 Not applicable.

10

11 **A.7.3 Availability of data and materials**

12 The data that support the findings of this study are available from Pfizer, Inc., but
13 restrictions apply to the availability of these data, which were used under license for the
14 current study, and so are not publicly available. Data are however available from the
15 authors upon reasonable request and with permission of Pfizer, Inc.

16 **A.7.4 Competing interests**

17 DT has no competing interests.

18 SR is an employee of Pfizer, Inc. He is also stockholder of Pfizer, Inc. and Novartis
19 Pharmaceutical.

20 CDA has no competing interests.

1 DR contributes to a university-based statistical consulting service that has received limited
2 consulting fees from Pfizer, no personal fees.

3 JZM has no competing interests.

4 WS has no competing interests.

5 EG contribute to a university-based statistical consulting service that has received limited
6 consulting fees from Pfizer, no personal fees.

7 SIC has no competing interests.

8

9 **A.7.5 Funding**

10 The SISAQOL-IMI project has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2
11 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 945052. This Joint Undertaking receives
12 support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and
13 EFPIA.

14 **A.7.6 Authors' contributions**

15 Conception and study design: SIC, EG, DT, with input from all authors. Data acquisition: SR,
16 SIC and EG. Data analysis, preparing figures and tables: DT with supervision of SIC, EG, SR.
17 Interpretation of data: DT, SIC, EG, CDA, SR, DR, JZM, WS. Manuscript - writing the first
18 draft: DT. Manuscript – review and editing: DT, SIC, EG, DR, CDA, SR, JZM, WS. All SISAQOL-
19 WP3 members reviewed the manuscript before submission.

1 **A.7.7 Acknowledgements**

2 We would like to thank the STRATOS Initiative for their valuable methodological input
3 during this study, and their members' involvement in SISAQOL-IMI Work Package 3.

4 This publication reflects the views of the individual authors and should not be construed to
5 represent official views or policies of the European Medicines Agency (EMA), the US Food
6 and Drug Administration (FDA), US National Cancer Institute (NCI), Medicines and
7 Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA), Institute for Quality and Efficiency in
8 Health Care (IQWiG), Health Canada, the Norwegian Medicines Agency (NOMA), the
9 American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) or the European Society for Medical
10 Oncology (ESMO) or any other institution, organization, or entity. This publication reflects
11 the authors' view and that neither IMI nor the EU, EFPIA are responsible for any use that
12 may be made of the information contained therein.

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9

10 **A.9 SISAQOL-IMI Work Package 3**

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1 **APPENDIX: The role of the estimand framework in the analysis** 2 **of patient-reported outcomes in single-arm trials: a case study** 3 **in oncology**

4 **A.1 Supplement on missing data imputation**

5 **A.1.1 Motivation for our imputation model**

6 In this case study, we intended to deal with the issue of missing PRO data separately from
7 the illustration of the estimand framework. We plan to elaborate on missing longitudinal
8 PRO data in the presence of intercurrent events further in future work. The objective of our
9 imputation for this case study was to keep it simple and create a single complete dataset
10 that could serve as an example. We therefore used a single imputation method here,
11 acknowledging that a multiple imputation method would be preferred in a real trial
12 analysis because it accounts better for imputation uncertainty. Two focus points for the
13 imputation were: (1) no imputation of QoL values after death; and (2) take the occurrence
14 and timing of intercurrent events (death, progression of disease, treatment
15 discontinuation) into account in the imputation of QoL.

16 Since the treatment was only available within the trial, treatment discontinuation was
17 observed at some time point for all participants. A time of disease progression was not
18 recorded for everyone. In this case study, we assumed that all death was disease-related
19 (since participants had an advanced stage of lung cancer and the mortality rate was high),
20 and if no PD was recorded before death, the date of death was set as the PD date. Those for
21 whom no PD was recorded and who were censored for overall survival, were censored for
22 PD at the overall survival censoring date.

1 In the available data, we summarized the PRO measurements backwards from death and
2 censoring, setting the clock to zero at death or censoring. We found that on average, PRO
3 scores dropped in the last five cycles before death, whereas no such drop was observed
4 before censoring. The progression of disease and the decision to discontinue treatment
5 may be related to patients' QoL trajectories as well. We therefore assumed that the time-
6 distance to death and other intercurrent events was possibly relevant to the missing PROs
7 at each cycle.

8 **A.1.2 Imputation model specification**

9 We imputed missing PRO data using single imputation until cycle 40, under the assumption
10 that the PROs at each cycle were missing at random conditional on the cycle number,
11 available QoL measurements at other cycles, death, PD and TD, and the time until these
12 events. We used a linear mixed model with a random patient-intercept. Variables included
13 were the cycle number (forward time scale), the number of cycles till death/PD/TD
14 (backward time scales), time-varying indicators of whether PD/TD had occurred, and
15 constant indicators of whether PD/death was observed or censored. Splines were applied
16 for all backward time variables. We also included an interaction between the cycles till
17 death/PD and the corresponding censoring indicators. This means that we assumed the
18 time-relation between QoL and death/PD to be different from the time-relation between
19 QoL and censoring (for survival and PD, respectively).

20 Our method to address missing PROs is informed by the occurrence and timing of ICEs,
21 which may be observed after the missing PRO was planned to be measured. For this reason,
22 direct likelihood-based methods where a mixed model is used for the implicit imputation

1 and analysis of PROs at the same time would not be appropriate. While the information on
2 (future) ICEs may be informative for the missing values, conditioning on future values in an
3 analysis model would not target the estimand of interest. Therefore, to take ICE
4 information into account, we opted to handle missing PRO values using a missing data
5 model that was separate from the substantive analysis model.

6 Specifically, our imputation model was coded in R as follows:

```
7 lmer(QL2 ~ (1|patid) + as.factor(cycleno) + rms::rsc(cycles_till_PD,nk=4,  
8 knots = c(1,4, 9,20))*PD_observed + rms::rsc(cycles_till_TD,nk=4, knots =  
9 c(1,4, 9,20)) + rms::rsc(cycles_till_end,nk=4, knots = c(1,4,  
10 9,20))*death_observed + PD_yet + TD_yet, ...)
```

11 Patient-specific predictions from this model were used to impute missing QoL values. In
12 our subsequent analyses, we assumed non-informative censoring in our analyses, as the
13 majority of censoring was administrative censoring. In cases where the assumption of
14 uninformative censoring is unlikely to hold, reweighing techniques based on the inverse
15 probability of censoring might be applied.

16 **A.1.3 Results**

17 The PRO means are slightly lower in the imputed dataset than in the available data. This
18 was to be expected, as a large proportion of PROs were missing shortly before death, and in
19 those which were available, we noted a drop before death (Figure S6). This drop was
20 modelled in the imputation, leading to a larger proportion of lower QoL values in later
21 cycles in the imputed dataset. Patients in a worse disease stage may have more
22 intermittent missing PROs as well.

1

2 *Figure S6. Mean reported global quality of life at each cycle, within the available data and*
 3 *within the dataset where missing values were imputed. All means are while alive and not*
 4 *censored.*

5 **A.2 Applying the estimand framework to PROs in a single-arm trial: a**
 6 **review of possible choices**

7 **A.2.1 Defining the variable of interest**

8 **A.2.1.1 The absolute (numerical or ordinal) values of the PRO**

9 Analyzing the absolute numerical PRO values at (a) prespecified time(s) is most
 10 straightforward and avoids information loss in outcome post-processing(1).

11 **A.2.1.2 Magnitude of change from baseline**

12 The PRO change from baseline subtracts a person’s baseline value from their absolute PRO
 13 value at each cycle. With this choice of variable, we must consider ceiling and floor effects,

1 since most PROs have a maximum and minimum possible value. Patients starting at the
2 maximum (minimum) value can never have a positive (negative) change from baseline.
3 Furthermore, if a clinically important change is defined on the individual patient level,
4 patients whose baseline value is closer to the maximum/minimum than this change, can
5 never experience such change (in the positive/negative direction, respectively), regardless
6 of the effect of treatment.

7 When the baseline PRO is predictive for survival, trends in change from baseline scores in
8 those alive may reflect the selection process due to death on the baseline values rather than
9 an effect of the treatment on the PROs over time. Also, change scores have been shown not
10 to generally estimate the intended causal effect in observational data(2), depending on the
11 causal relation between the baseline score and later scores. In addition, regression to the
12 mean and measurement error may affect observed change scores. Finally, the analysis of
13 change scores is known to be statistically inefficient compared to an analysis of covariance
14 with the baseline score as a covariate(3).

15 **A.2.1.3 Responder/non-responder classification**

16 A third potential choice of variable is to classify patients as responders or non-
17 responders—overall or at each cycle. For example, patients could be classified as
18 ‘responder’ when their QoL values reach some threshold or increase by some amount.

19 A patient’s QoL reaching a threshold or having improved a certain amount from baseline
20 are not necessarily definitive events; patients may deteriorate after having improved and
21 vice versa. Classifying patients as overall responder or non-responder does not reflect this

1 aspect of the individual patterns over time. When response is defined by a minimum
2 improvement from baseline, ceiling and bottom effects may apply as well.

3 In addition, when defining overall responders, it is important to incorporate a relevant
4 time-window in which the response must have occurred. Depending on the analysis, bias
5 may arise when patients are more likely to become responders when they remain alive
6 longer. Still, missing PRO values can lead to the timing of response being unknown. Another
7 consideration is that any type of responder classification may create an artificial dichotomy
8 between patients whose original QoL patterns are not very different qualitatively(4,5).

9 **A.2.1.4 Time to event: time to deterioration and time to response**

10 When response or deterioration are definitive events, or when the time until the first such
11 event is meaningful, a time-to-event variable may be of interest. Time till deterioration
12 endpoints for PROs may be familiar to trialists in oncology, because of their analogy with
13 progression free survival (PFS) as a clinical endpoint.

14 The considerations for responder classification outlined above apply here as well, in
15 particular the possibly non-definitive nature of response and deterioration. An additional
16 complication in time-to-event analysis of PROs is that a drop or rise in the outcome is
17 recorded at the next time a questionnaire is filled in (if the PRO has not changed again).
18 Therefore, the exact time of response or deterioration is only known to lie between two
19 assessments (interval censoring). In a recent paper, Fiero et al.(6) suggest an analysis at
20 pre-specified relevant timepoints rather than a time-to-event approach.

1 **A.2.2 Population level summary**

2 When the aim of the study is descriptive, the mean variable in each cycle may be a suitable
3 population level summary of the absolute values of the PRO and changes from baseline. For
4 responder classification, the proportion of responders in relevant cycles may be of interest.
5 A time-to-event variable may be summarized with an estimate of the probability of the
6 event over time. Sometimes a single summary value is of interest, e.g., when external
7 comparisons are made for benchmarking. The mean variable at one or several prespecified,
8 relevant time points is then another option.

9 **A.2.3 Strategies for dealing with intercurrent events and death**

10 The ICH E9 (R1)⁴ defines intercurrent events (IEs) as events that occur after the start of a
11 trial and affect the presence and/or interpretability of observed outcome values. We focus
12 on three such events: death, disease progression (PD), treatment discontinuation (TD).

13 The estimand framework suggests five strategies for handling intercurrent events in an
14 analysis. The chosen strategy should reflect the study aim, as it will determine the
15 interpretation of the results of the analysis.

16 **A.2.3.1 ‘While the intercurrent event has not yet occurred’–strategy**

17 This strategy entails that we aim to obtain our population level summary at each relevant
18 time point for those patients who are still without the IE at that time point. For death, for
19 instance, this means we are interested in the PROs of those patients who are still alive
20 (while alive strategy).

1 **A.2.3.2 Composite strategy**

2 Sometimes the outcome of interest and the intercurrent event are combined into a
3 different, composite outcome. An example is QoL measured with EQ-5D, where a value of 0
4 is defined for QoL after death. Another example is a time-till-deterioration endpoint where
5 deterioration is defined as QoL below a certain value or death.

6 **A.2.3.3 Hypothetical strategy**

7 A third strategy is to estimate the population level summary in a hypothetical world where
8 the intercurrent event could be postponed until after the end of the trial for all patients. A
9 corresponding example estimand would be the mean QoL at cycle 10, if no one would die
10 or discontinue treatment before cycle 10.

11 **A.2.3.4 Treatment policy strategy**

12 A treatment policy strategy ignores the intercurrent event in the analysis. This reflects the
13 intention-to-treat principle: the treatment effect is estimated based on assigned treatment
14 at study onset, regardless of what happens afterwards. The estimated effect aims to
15 represent the effect of a treatment policy. After death, however, PRO values do not exist,
16 hence death cannot be ignored in the analysis⁴.

17 **A.2.3.5 Principal stratum strategy**

18 A principal stratum is a subgroup of patients who would or who would not have
19 experienced the event under either of the treatments in a study. For death, a principal
20 stratum might be those patients who would have survived during the study, irrespective of
21 treatment received. A corresponding estimand would be the difference in mean outcome

1 for treatment A vs B, in those surviving the study, regardless of their treatment assignment.
2 A patient's intercurrent events can only be observed for the treatment arm they were
3 actually in, so the principal stratum strategy requires counterfactual information about
4 whether they would have had the event, had they been assigned to the other treatment
5 arm. Since the focus of this report is on single-arm trials, where there is only one treatment
6 in the study, we did not apply a principal stratum strategy.

7 **A.3 Supplementary figures and tables**

8
9 *Figure S7. Kaplan-Meier estimate of the probability of overall survival in our case study*
10 *cohort.*
11

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	Overall (N=876)
Sex	
Female	501 (57.2%)
Male	375 (42.8%)
Age (years)	
Mean (SD)	53.0 (12.4)
No. of previous drug treatments	
1	181 (20.7%)
2	323 (36.9%)
3	189 (21.6%)
4	91 (10.4%)
5	49 (5.6%)
6	22 (2.5%)
> 6	21 (2.4%)
ECOG performance status at baseline	
0	249 (28.4%)
1	480 (54.8%)
2	119 (13.6%)
3	28 (3.2%)
Days to treatment discontinuation	
Median [Min, Max]	327 [1.00, 1690]
Days to first disease progression	
Median [Min, Max]	249 [6.00, 1550]
Missing	228 (26.0%)
Death observed	
No	300 (34.2%)
Yes	576 (65.8%)
Objective tumor response observed	
No	411 (46.9%)
Yes	465 (53.1%)

2 *Table S2. Demographical and clinical characteristics of the patients included in our case*
3 *study.*

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Figure S8. Kaplan-Meier estimates of overall survival in our case study cohort, stratified by QoL at the start of protocol treatment (in participants who reported QoL in their first treatment cycle). Participants were stratified based on four intervals of baseline QoL values: [0, 25], [25, 50], [50, 75] and [75, 100]. The shaded regions represent 95% confidence intervals.

A. Time from last PRO to death
In those who died

B. Time from last PRO to censoring
In those who were censored

C. Time from last available PRO to TD

D. Time from last available PRO to PD

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Figure S9. Distributions of the time between the last available PRO measurement and death (A), censoring (B), treatment discontinuation (C) and progression of disease (D), respectively

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2 *Figure S10. Estimated mean global QoL and corresponding 95% CIs at the first and every fifth*
 3 *cycle, for a while alive, composite and hypothetical strategy to deal with death. No major*
 4 *differences in CI width occurred between the various analysis methods used.*

5

1

2 *Figure S11. Estimated mean global QoL and corresponding 95% CIs at the first and every fifth*
 3 *cycle, for various strategies to deal with treatment discontinuation.*

4

5

1
 2 *Figure S12. Estimated mean global QoL and corresponding 95% CIs at the first and every fifth*
 3 *cycle, for various strategies to deal with disease progression.*

A.4 References

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